

Analysis of the English Language Teachers' Constraints in Implementing Outcome-Based Educational Approach for Engineering Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 28, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 30, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Outcome-Based Education (OBE), Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC), English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Engineering Curriculum, Teachers' Attitude.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7783402</p>	<p><i>The outcome-Based Educational (OBE) approach in teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is considered the emerging trend that has been adopted in educational institutions worldwide. It shows a shift from the input-based traditional teaching approaches to the specific outcome-based approach. The Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) has made it mandatory for the curriculum to be OBE based for universities offering engineering programs. Although attempts are made to follow the OBE approach, the constraints of the practitioners have yet to be determined for the effective implementation of OBE-based education. The study aims to determine the constraints English language teachers face in implementing the OBE approach in the ESP classroom of engineering students in Pakistan. For the study, the qualitative method has been used to collect the data from the English language teachers through semi-structured interviews. A four-step Interview Protocol Refinement (IPR) Framework was adopted to get the best possible quality data for refining semi-structured interviews. The study concludes that achieving desired results in engineering education, especially English courses, requires skills, traits and knowledge. The results indicate that though the respondents show a positive attitude towards OBE in the ESP classroom, lack of teacher training, and ignorance of technical details are the impediments.</i></p>

Introduction

To provide a suitable teaching methodology to engineers, the Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) has mandated that engineering programs offered in Pakistani universities have a curriculum based on Outcome-Based Education (OBE). It is the responsibility of higher education institutions and teachers to ensure that students get relevant knowledge from their degree programs. It also includes skills, attitudes and values that accompany a country's social, economic and cultural environment.

Altogether, a shift from content-based to outcome-based education has been observed in the higher education set-up in Pakistan (Manzoor et al., 2017). Because of the Washington Accord, formed in 1989, several countries, including Pakistan, signed an agreement to accept the OBE method to teach engineering students (Yoshida, 2019). Following this, a few years back, in the education sector of Pakistan, this curriculum model gained the attention of practitioners and researchers. It was implemented to produce competitive graduates for a country, and for this teaching, faculty should be able to prioritize students' skills which they must achieve from their engineering studies for their livelihood (Passow and Passow, 2017).

OBE is a classical educational theory and brainchild presented by the sociologist Spady William in 1994 (Yang, 2019; Qadir et al., 2020). This term originates from Wilson's (1994) behaviourism, called performance-based and outcome-based education. It pays close attention to organizing curriculum, which is essential for students' successful learning experience (Zhang, Xuan and Zhang, 2020). In this method, the learning outcomes of the entire program are connected under OBE, curriculum, instruction, and assessments (Shaheen, 2019; Mallikarjuna, 2020). It is in the transitional stage and needs continuous research to achieve desired outcomes; performances must be measured through those outcomes (Rajak, Shrivastava and Shrivastava, 2018). It emphasizes formative criterion-based assessment, in contrast to summative assessment, embracing a developmental approach to education and focuses on engineering students' learning outcomes that are pre-decided to be achieved.

One goal of OBE is to function as a bridge between education and employability. The OBE theory is a combination of many studies on pedagogical methods (Masters and Evans, 1986; Guskey, 2007; Tyler, 2013), and in practice, the concept of OBE is more than following a single idea or a set of procedures and works as an independent procedure (Lawson and Askill-Williams, 2007). Opposite to other traditional models, the focus of OBE remains connected with the assessment of learners' knowledge (Nakkeeran et al., 2018) and Course Learning Outcomes (CLO) (Willis and Kissane, 1997; Lawson and Askill-Williams, 2007). OBE can be challenging as it puts students at the front while transforming the role of the teacher into a helper in the learning

process (Jenkins, Healey, and Zetter, 2008). It also provides a framework for organizing the curriculum around predetermined and defined student learning outcomes (Custodio, Espita and Siy, 2019). Overall, it highlights a need for tertiary education where engineering students also take care of professional knowledge and skills to meet the diversified yet global demands of the 21st century.

There is no doubt that all over the globe, OBE has been adopted by educational systems (Spady, 1994; Custodio, Espita and Siy, 2019), but most of the OBE courses in the past have used the existing course outlines without an understanding of the intended outcomes that move beyond the curriculum for the students (Spady and Marshall, 1991). As the OBE method is designed to increase student learning, concerns related to its implementation have not been fully explored. Its primary concern lies in its final assessment, in that the aims of the immediate course may vary from the program's established objectives (Boud, 2000). It was also hinted by Spady (1991) that time-bound structure and delivery methods might also affect OBE methods. A study by Cruz and Kellam (2018) shows that engineering students must be trained by teachers and peers in a way that they develop an understanding of their relative field and perform well in difficult everyday situations. The problem arises when we observe hindrances faced by teachers in implementing it in Pakistan.

A Pakistani study by Pirzada and Gul (2019) pinpointed that people in Pakistan are not fully aware of the general conceptualization and utility of OBE. Also, the lack of in-depth understanding of this system has mainly affected all other survey sections. Thus, this study aims to shed light on the primary constraints of the English faculty to implement OBE in the result-oriented curriculum for English for Specific Purposes (ESP). It refers to teaching the English Language for specific purposes or skills; for instance, engineering students are taught particular vocabulary, which creates an understanding with their engineering education) in the BS program at the National University of Computer and Emerging Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan.

OBE is designing a curriculum, teaching and assessing students' learning. It mainly relies on students, assessing *what* and *whether* students can learn successfully. The process of OBE follows three main stages or forms. The primary form of OBE showed that students could not follow the basic disciplines, such as following learning outcomes parameters. The second form of OBE is to maintain quality for the assessment at an institutional level to assess knowledge, skills, values or attributes to progress in education; the third form is Outcome Based Teaching and Learning (BTL), in which outcomes are designed to enhance teaching and assessment and teachers are supposed to make students learn the specified course (Yusof et al., 2017).

OBE system is best understood by Spady's 5 P's Pyramid, shown in image no 1.

Image 1

Image 1 shows Spady's OBE Pyramid-The 5 P's.

Image 1 has been taken from the study by Qadir et al. (2020), which explained as central ideas of OBE. It explains that students' learning is the primary motive for which methods are developed and the designing of a curriculum is planned. Paradigm, the top, relates to the completion of successful students' learning, which is dependent upon understanding objectives/ purposes, premises, principles and practices. The purpose of their learning must be understood about students' needs and requirements as they are not the same and share different premises. Also, the principles and practices act as a base and play a significant role in developing the OBE pyramid.

Moreover, the 3 T's are also discussed by Spady (1998), i.e. *Traditional, Transitional and Transformational*. OBE has three types of approaches defined by Spady and his followers. Those three types are named 3Ts, in which *traditional OBE* focuses a command on traditional subjects and persuades educators to take their prevailing curriculum content and structure and set up outcomes. *Transitional OBE* lies between *traditional* and *transformational* and strives for learners' ultimate problem-solving abilities with technology, curriculum and assessment. Lastly, *transformational OBE* equips each learner with the skills, knowledge and attitude for the future to show practical ability, which is not only successful but also technologically radical (Shaheen, 2019).

In this study, we aim to seek English language teachers' constraints regarding the readiness and teaching effectiveness for a transition mandated by the accreditation board from content-based education to an outcome-based model. The study's objective is to describe the teaching constraints while asking about faculty experiences and determine the extent of development in the OBE transition process for a possible way forward.

1. Literature Review

The following literature highlights studies related to the following: 1) General English and English for Specific Purposes (ESP); 2) ESP courses and OBE; 3) English Language Teachers and OBE; 4) Engineering Education and OBE in Pakistan. It shows several studies that have explored ways of teaching the English Language for specific purposes. It further shows that Outcome-Based Education (OBE) is adopted for English for Specific Purposes (ESP) classrooms worldwide and, more specifically, in Pakistan.

2.1. Importance of the English Language

English has been taught in Pakistani institutes since 1947 (Tanoli, n.d); the research also confirms that teaching every subject must be in English (Mahboob, 2003). Several studies showed that a country's productivity and ability to meet global economic challenges are based on quality education. At the same time, all over the globe, the English Language is considered to be an effective communication tool because of its relation to academia, business and science (Dar, Zaki, & Kazmi, 2010; Shamim, 2011; YousafZai and Fareed, 2019). Like other professionals, engineers are also future leaders in their fields, and it is necessary to give importance to English language teaching for engineering students. They must be able to solve complex problems (Benson et al., 2010; Kirn and Benson, 2018; Helmi, Mohd-Yusof, and Hisham, 2019), which is a need of the current time. It helps future engineers to develop a better understanding of daily problems and global challenges. Therefore, there is pressure on multilingual scholars, which pushes them to be prepared and well-informed for international standards of the English Language (Custodio, Espita and Siy, 2019; Bardi and Muresan, 2020).

1.2. General English and English for Specific Purposes (ESP)

The term ESP was noticed in the 1960s when people, especially employers, became aware that general English cannot meet their wants (Brunton, 2019). Tan and Balasco (2018) pointed out that in Asian countries, the English Language is considered one of the significant subjects in selecting a career. It was further emphasized that general English or generic skills could not be as influential as specific English skills (Chan, Zhao and Luk, 2017). Liu (2016) defines general English as essential awareness in all fields. While on the other side, with every passing day, the world is moving towards betterment with several new demands and specific challenges in every field. Thus specific English, which is the need of the time, is also developing quickly (Xu and Sun, 2019). Furthermore, it has been noticed that students who perform well in English also perform expertly in their respective professions (Sek, Mok, Leung and Li, 2018). Therefore, specific English has a fundamental role in this challenging world, and students must be taught English for specific purposes with well-suited materials. These must be developed while noticing elements such as needs analysis, language components, specific vocabulary, and content and topic selection, as they are considered to be unlike general ones. Anirudh (2019) further highlighted that it is challenging to prepare relevant materials, including contents, language components and the approaches/methods for teaching.

1.3. ESP Courses and Outcome-Based Education (OBE)

ESP courses are gaining much more due attention in the education system of Pakistan and therefore require further studies. Overall, the idea of such courses is to make students "empowered in their respective fields" (Khan, 2019). Similarly, OBE works to achieve the 5 P's, where learning outcomes of the entire program are planned. (Sukerti, Yuliantini and Susana, 2020). The technicalities involved in breaking up the course contents into smaller units as per the OBE course learning objectives (CLO); not only affect the communication objectives of the ESP course but also become impractical in specific contexts. Also, the assessment methods recommended in the OBE curriculum have burdened the teachers to the extent that the assessments have become synonymous with extra work. The teachers are constantly on the go, creating material for formative and summative exams. For best teaching, they require supportive conditions and resources that facilitate their development, as discussed by Van Den Beemt et al. (2020).

Outcome-based education (OBE) is a method which focuses on the organization of an entire program's outcomes. At the same time, English for specific purposes (ESP) is related to one subject, i.e. English, which is taught for specific (technical) purposes. For example, an English course in an engineering program is organized according to the OBE approach, which can be called an Outcome-based ESP course. A few studies defined ESP courses based on OBE principles as Outcome-based (Du, Wang and Yu, 2019; Sukerti, Yuliantini and Susana, 2020). ESP is defined as a design for students who want to work in certain fields and want to prosper in that specific field. As mentioned by Suganiya (2019) that ESP courses help to achieve "enhancement of expertise in specific fields"; make English learners able to adjust in "legitimate and target situations", and help in a process to make "professional communication" better (Jiajing, 2007). Du and Wang (2019) highlighted that ESP courses help satisfy learners whose needs are examined, decisions regarding teaching objectives are made, and different tasks are designed.

Another study by Gestanti, Nimasari and Mufanti (2019) mentioned the needs of students in an ESP course at a private university in Indonesia. It elaborated that students require distinguished ESP materials, for example, activities and show that the material is not general. Moreover, encouragement from teachers conveys "autonomous learning" and makes students independent to perform and speak well in the classroom. Also, Zeng (2019) mentioned that learning activities could be designed where teachers act as facilitators to accomplish the tasks. Moreover, OBE works to improve their targeted language learning process (Wozniak, 2010; Ibrahim, 2010; Salehi, Davari and Yunus, 2015; Nakkeeran, 2018; Gestanti, Nimasari and Mufanti, 2019). ESP courses in many countries are mainly planned for the Grade 12 university students, such as undergraduates, because they use specific vocabulary and grammar (Simion and Genova, 2019). Similarly, OBE focuses on defining the quantifiable learning outcomes students are expected to acquire when they graduate.

1.4. English Language Teachers and Outcome Based Education (OBE)

Several researchers also claim that English language teachers lack sufficient knowledge in decoding language-related concepts, especially engineering, commerce and medicine students' communication skills (Saqlain, Qazi and Simon, 2012; Buriro & Soomro, 2013). However, Pakistani and other studies suggest that English language teachers can teach ESP courses if they have thorough command and understanding of Language, pedagogy and learners' needs (Rajabi, Kiany and Maftoon, 2011; Zoghi and Farsi, 2014; Estaji & Nazari, 2015; Yousaf Zai and Fareed, 2019). Similarly, Conard's (2017) study also revealed that student writing problems could be addressed through instructional materials to provide better results and improve ESP course teaching.

A study by Pirzada and Gull (2019) employed data from the teachers of universities, colleges and institutes in Pakistan who have experience or potential to adopt OBE. Their study showed that awareness creates the potential for OBE, which is still missing in many institutions and teaching resources. Similarly, a case study of two countries in, Bulgaria and Romania, by Simion and Genova (2019) highlighted that OBE does not require any specific style of teaching and it should be based on students' needs; class activities, assessments and tasks help students to achieve desired results (Yang, 2019). Genova (2019) pointed out the status of teaching ESP by providing detailed information about the language background of universities. It was further emphasized by Yang (2019) that for the students' betterment and learning process, sufficient learning resources and specific learning guides should be provided to students. Their study suggested a need to keep learning resources exciting and clear. Also, teachers must screen, control and assess students' learning cycles and offer help to improve the learning impact of ESP courses.

A lot of studies also mentioned that teachers should consider the development goals and requirements of every course. By doing this, every course will be designed in such a way as to help students in achieving specific learning outcomes, which is considerable in OBE (Tuyen, 2018). Also, learners can gain "continuous improvement" (Zeng, 2019). A recent study of Romania by Bardi and Muresan (2020) mentioned that improving academic capabilities is challenging. The study explored the new roles of ESP for subject specialists such as economics and business. The results show that noticing students' needs and adapting to suitable teaching methods is challenging but brings professional development chances for language teaching academics.

Another study by Custodio, Espita and Siy (2019) also explored OBE within the university and identified areas for improvement. Their study showed that OBE is helpful in critical thinking, acquiring relevant knowledge and skills to solve problems and developing professional ethics. Another study by Qadir et al. (2020) provided shared perspectives for strategic vision, quality management and assessment. Their study mentioned OBE as a "flexible method" because it gives liberty in selecting suitable strategies for specific education while its primary focus remains on the outcome. Moreover, a Saudi Arabian study by Umer and Soomro (2019) describes OBE with the Saudi framework by evaluating summative examinations of 9 randomly selected English language courses. Their documentary-based study confirms that maintaining a positive balance of assessments and CLOs is somewhat impossible in a few language teaching contexts.

1.5. Engineering Education and Outcome-Based Education (OBE) in Pakistan

Several researchers have discussed OBE concerning engineering programs in Pakistan. For example, according to the Washington accord, a study by Mahmood et al. (2015) describes the initial introduction of the

OBE approach in Pakistani BS engineering programs. It discusses the EE221 course titled Signal and Systems according to the rules of OBE and shows that meeting the Washington accord's criteria to improve students' performances is complex and requires continuous feedback, proposals and necessary implementations. Similarly, Rashid (2012) highlighted the necessary terminologies related to OBE. Such as the term Program outcomes or (POs) is used for programs, Student learning outcomes (SLOs) which are based on the individual learning of a student depending upon his or her need, Course learning outcomes (CLOs) which are specific course requirements, Learning Outcomes (LOs) is a general term. In contrast, Chapter learning outcomes (Cos) are more specific and related to a chapter. It was also mentioned by Balasubramani and Chiplunkar (2017) that COs are the source of attaining POs.

Likewise, another Pakistani study by Kamran et al. (2020) also presented the implementation of the OBE, and the results highlighted that the OBE truly helps to analyze the industrial and academic outcomes of the programs. Their study explained three related points, including OBE's assessment policy, which includes Alumni and employer feedback, Program Learning Outcomes (PLOs) and Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs). It further explained each term where PLOs are those expected attributes a graduate should acquire after completing the degree and should be able to apply in his or her professional life. Whereas CLOs are outcomes that the specific instructor of each course defines for the completion of the course contents and ensures that every CLO also meets the criteria of PLO.

Moreover, a Pakistani study by Yasmin, Naseem and Abas (2019) discussed 16 university teachers' perspectives on the constraints in learner autonomy and showed sociocultural, institutional and psychological hurdles of Pakistani culture. Despite progress and continuing revolutions in technical education set up in Pakistan, some cultural challenges are present. For instance, males are allowed and found more interested in such programs. In engineering programs, almost 90% are males and 10 % females because females are dependent on families for taking a decision and males are preferred and encouraged by their families to get such formal and technical education (Svanemyr, Baig and Chandra-Mouli, 2015). Similarly, Qadir et al. (2020) mentioned that though there is a given set of OBE practices worldwide, every university shows some differences while implementing it. In Pakistan, OBE is implemented, but there is a need to explore if OBE is adopted as original or if there are some variances. Qadir et al. (2020) mentioned that the common point is to increase expectations regarding learning outcomes, but changes do exist when resource persons and institutes try to perform it in their way "without really understanding the rationale of OBE". It may result in something different, which is not a forte of OBE because of the presence of new terms that "are easy to confuse and use incorrectly".

The research shows that OBE in the Pakistani context is not easy to adopt because of the conventional system of education, which is why teachers, institutes, parents and employers must ensure to implement it. For this, Shaheen (2019) pinpointed twelve challenges related to the implementation of OBE in Pakistan, which include Acceptability, Paradigm Shift, Maintain Quality of Education, Restructure Outcomes and Assessment techniques, OBE as top Precedence, Design down Approach, Impacts on Students with Special Needs, Teacher's Role, Responsibility of successful learning, Break typecast, Wave of opposition, Perception of students and teachers. Currently, Pakistan faces almost all challenges, and studies show dependency on administration, teachers and students. The study further suggests that this approach must be explored through extensive research.

Although researchers have started exploring OBE in other courses of the undergraduate Engineering program, there is little research about OBE in English language courses in a Pakistani context. Therefore, there is a need to explore the constraints the English language teachers face in implementing the OBE approach in the ESP classroom for engineering students.

Methodology

The study followed a face-to-face semi-structured interview protocol. It was designed by us to collect qualitative data from the teaching staff. These in-depth interviews were carried out with the teaching staff focusing on their teaching constraints and/or challenges in implementing the OBE curriculum.

Interviews are considered beneficial because they can help explore conversations in a natural setting (Kvale, 1996; 2007). We adopted a four-step Interview Protocol Refinement (IPR) Framework to get the possible quality data for refining semi-structured interviews because it is considered the most suitable and convenient approach for data collection in these studies (Castillo-Montoya, 2016; Yeong et al., 2018). Firstly, we ensured that the interview questions were connected with the research questions and developed an inquiry-based conversation. Feedback was also taken from the experts about the pilot interview questions to strengthen the connection between the research question and interview protocol. It helped improve the interview protocol's reliability and validity (Walther, Sochacka and Kellam, 2013); and contributed to the refinement of research data collected from the interviewees (Castillo-Montoya, 2016). The interview protocol included questions

focusing on teachers' current teaching beliefs and practices, expectations from students, areas for improvement in their teaching, and constraints they faced.

Semi-structured interviews are the most common qualitative research method (Alvesson and Deetz, 2000, p. 194; Dörnyei, 2007, p.132) and effective means of gathering information (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009) by social scientists. It develops insights about the participants with care and thorough planning (Qu and Dumay, 2011). This type in qualitative approach is adopted for the recording and accumulation of human behaviour in given situations. According to Brown (2004) “forming hypothesis is one of the great strengths of qualitative research”.

3.1. Setting and Participants

The OBE method has been fully implemented on the entire curriculum of the Electrical Engineering (EE) program at the National University of Computer and Emerging Sciences (NUCES) FAST, Lahore campus, Pakistan. As part of the change to OBE methodology in the Electrical Engineering (EE) discipline, twelve faculty members, including two male and ten female Pakistani teachers, teaching the two-credit hour ESP course to the EE students constituted the sample for the study. This course is part of the curriculum in the first year of an engineering program and makes about 6 to 8 sections of 25 students each, depending upon the admission intake.

The study participants, English teachers, have completed a minimum of two years and a maximum of five years of teaching ESP courses to engineering students. Therefore, they were interviewed to share their teaching experiences about OBE implementation constraints. All faculty members are qualified with at least a Master's degree in English Language Teaching (ELT) or Applied Linguistics (AL). In addition, two professors hold PhD in English and lead others in preparing CLOs for the EE program at a university. An email was sent to invite faculty members for the interviews, and in-person, one-to-one interviews were conducted with them. It means that it was done with one participant at a time, depending upon their availability for full involvement in our research. All necessary permissions to conduct the study were obtained from the Humanities department. The faculty members were informed of the confidentiality of the interviews.

3.2 Data Collection and Data Analysis

All interviews were recorded and transcribed (Emilia, 2005) and then were arranged by category (Creswell, 2012). The results were analyzed for consistent themes by using thematic analysis to discover themes in the transcriptions of the interviews, focusing on the difficulties faced in enabling student learning and achieving an outcome-based instructional model within the current academic framework. This method was used because it "reports experiences, meanings and reality of participants" (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 9). Furthermore, we then summarised the emerging themes (Emilia, 2005) for refinement and clarity where necessary.

conclude that research ethics is not something we should do for its own sake or because we are compelled to by regulatory bodies, but something we must do to improve the quality of our interpretive research findings

Findings

The present study's findings focus on the views of English language teachers as participants on their readiness for a transition from content-based teaching to an outcome-based model to fill the gap between the educational policy and the actual implementation of OBE. The results from the qualitative data helped us to maintain an in-depth understanding of the interviewees' experience and constraints to implementing OBE in English language classrooms. Also, they helped us identify essential elements relevant to the research objectives. The results described the teachers' constraints in their teaching practices in the outcome-based ESP classroom.

This part is divided into several sections, highlighted as central themes and shows the main points to elaborate the study findings further. These include 1) the Gap between outcomes and reality constraints; 2) Students' Existing Knowledge versus Expected Outcomes; 3) Students' Assessment; 4) Teacher Training Constraints; and 5) Teacher Practice Constraints.

4.1. Gap between outcomes and reality constraints

Teachers were asked questions to share their teaching experience and method for teaching engineering students in English language classrooms. Moreover, how do they compare the traditional teaching method to OBE for engineering students? Most of the teachers interviewed claimed that their main teaching objective was transferring information to students. They mentioned it as "conveying information", "passing on knowledge", imparting and providing awareness, and covering the course, suggesting that the goals set by the OBE curriculum were not the focus of the current teaching plans. All teachers agreed that the effort required to tailor the ESP course to fit in with the OBE guidelines was a real challenge, as they did not know if they were focusing on the right expectations. A teacher said, "*Changing the teaching approaches is difficult, as they were confident of the old tried and tested methods to engage students in the classroom*". Another teacher added, "*...new methods are not always workable*". Another teacher said, "*To follow OBE structure, notes preparation,*

questions and rubrics has become a repetitive duty of teachers. It is not only time taking but also causes disturbance in preparation to meet the objectives and change students' needs".

Traditional education leans towards the curriculum to describe the teaching objectives that will be covered. The learner assessment is also determined by the objectives outlined in the curriculum. The link to the desired skills is defined once the curriculum is implemented—as an afterthought, as pointed out by Spady and Marshall (1991) earlier. At the same time, OBE sets the criteria to bring competency to students learning, ultimately deciding with the help of outcomes if the learner is competent. It was also claimed in Lawson and Askell-Williams's (2007) study that these outcomes show learners learning and require clear assessment standards, which are not a part of the current teaching practices. Thus, there remains a gap between outcomes and reality where teachers' complete preparation is required.

4.2. Students' Existing Knowledge Vs Expected Outcomes

Participants of the study were asked about the main factors they consider while preparing a lecture and course materials, contents, and method of instruction. Also, they were asked about students' capacity to learn according to the OBE method. Participants of the study stated that focus on individual learning in the class activities and the content creates differences in the classroom. Pakistani students from traditional backgrounds lack the requisite skills for learning in the interactive setting of a university. The OBE curriculum provides a chance to encourage individual learning, which could cause a deviation from the learning objectives reinforcing the views of Jenkins, Healey, and Zetter (2008) in their research.

Moreover, the shift for the teachers as a facilitator is not supported by the self-learning strategies the students are expected to have to be independent learners. A teacher said that *"lack of students' interest and absence from the lectures creates a big barrier to achieving expected outcomes"*. One of the teachers mentioned that *"it is not fully the teacher's responsibility to get herself fully prepared for outcome-based class; it is equally dependent on students"*. So here comes another challenge for teachers to prepare students for their future jobs. Another teacher mentioned that *".....a few students are not motivated in the classroom, and it becomes double to prepare them with a missing lecture in the next class"*.

A teacher said that *"it is in OBE approach makes teachers facilitators, but in this situation, where students are lagging behind the course contents, the teacher cannot make sure that students will complete the task to achieve maximum."*

So, another challenge highlighted by the teachers is the gap between OBE's desired features and those present in the redesigned course. The difference between the suggested learning outcomes and reality was of grave concern for the teachers teaching in the ESP classes. The teachers pointed out that most students could not think creatively; they could not manage the massive volume of information available to them in the constantly changing classroom situation. One of the teachers pointed out that although the students are inquisitive but lack a *"diverse understanding"* of their area for acquiring expertise. The teachers' answers reflect their apprehension about the students' resistance to change and unwillingness to practice their thinking skills creatively. Therefore, involving students and awakening their interest in desired OBE learning outcomes is necessary.

In answer to the question on abilities the learners must possess, one teacher responded, *"I asked them to read and answer the questions at the end, and most of them just google, looking at websites with irrelevant information... instead of reading and discussing the possible answer they spend more time trying to find the answer or wait for someone else to answer"*. Most teachers felt that students prefer to be passive recipients of information rather than actively involved in their learning. This conflict in the teachers' beliefs and student expectations can lead to insignificant evaluations. One teacher observed that the current situation might foster teachers working with unrealistic practices in the classroom. Another teacher described the prevailing learning behaviour: *"Teaching is different from facilitating. Students are passive when the teacher lectures ...but the students must come to class prepared to participate, not just to listen quietly"*. The teachers' comments revealed their uneasiness regarding the differences in the OBE projected goals and their teaching practices and objectives.

4.3. Students' Assessment

Participants were asked to describe an evaluation method of the OBE method. It was observed that one of the critical issues central to the OBE ways of assessing student work is the assessment both for formative and summative purposes. Firstly, to bring betterment for students in weak areas and secondly, to make final decisions on student proficiency are obligatory. As a result, the assessments are more frequent, rigorous and multidimensional. However, participants of the study showed that they are inclined towards the traditional end-of-term assessment pattern and lack training to conduct separately designed assessments. Hence, without proper training, making reliable judgments about learners' competency would not be productive, as Boud (2000) pointed out earlier in the review.

One of the teachers said, "teachers usually are found confused regarding student evaluation". Another teacher added, *"... rubrics are given with a scoring scheme, but still, it depends on the individual teacher, so it is not fixed..."*.

One participant emphasized the evaluation process in OBE; she said, *"Assessments and evaluations are so important as they help teachers to know the results of their efforts, next targets for improvements in teaching methods"*.

4.4. Teacher Training Constraints

Participants of the study were asked to share their OBE-related additional responsibilities and challenges. It was observed that the lack of training presents other problems, such as an inability to support individual students in their learning. Two teachers sought support from their colleagues, while three attended the workshop on remodelling the ESP course on OBE lines, and a few asked to be observed in the classroom during a class and provide feedback. The teacher mentioned that *"Outcome based English teaching is complex for engineering students and near to impossible without in-service training"*.

Training the university teachers to equip them with a contextualized understanding of OBE, learning domains, assessment techniques, course design and modern teaching pedagogies have been ignored. The training programs have yet to address the dilemma of weak content knowledge of OBE adequately. Most teachers are not trained to work according to the OBE aims. Additionally, the focus on excessive documentation has added to the existing teaching load in the ESP classroom (Seely, 1999). Sayed and Novelli (2016) mentioned that Initial Teacher Education (ITE) programmes must be introduced because they can impact diverse policy environments positively. The course learning objectives (CLOs) are mechanical and mandate prescriptive teaching, as substantiated by Willis and Kissane (1997) in their study. It is ambitious to expect that the teachers will be able to adjust to teaching the prescribed workload in the suggested timeframe, unaffected by everyday classroom situations.

4.5. Teaching Practice Constraints

The teachers showed that training and practice sessions are required to implement OBE in engineering classrooms. They believed that without proper practice, training is useless. They articulated their need to improve teaching practices and increase their knowledge of instructional choices to engage the students. Unfortunately, the teaching practices are overwhelmed by designing course outlines and class lessons with an emphasis on breaking the course into smaller units to meet the CLOs, which makes the tasks highly technical. These constraints have been underscored in literature by Jenkins, Healey, and Zetter (2008).

Moreover, regularly maintaining student performance records along with the CLOs mappings, the teachers often find their teaching goals shifted to more documentation rather than fulfilling the ESP course requirements, generating lengthy reports about lectures and students' assessments. Consequently, the study participants showed that they are less motivated to participate in research activities, highlighting the lack of quality on any significant scale or significant impact over time. For them, again, *"lack of appropriate practice sessions with or without training"* is the main reason for their demotivation and acts as a constraint in their effective teaching practices.

A teacher said, *"Pressure for language teachers is visible where results are required without practice or practical training"*. In addition, a teacher said that *"there is a strong need to work on teachers' personal growth and expertise which is unfortunately very rare"*. Another teacher added, *"...professional skills in this specialized are much needed"*.

Discussion

The present study highlights that the most common constraints are the lack of teacher training, the gap between learning outcomes and reality, and the redefining of teaching practices. Teacher characteristics and perceived roles were also discussed and often conflicted with those prescribed in the OBE model. Participants of the study, the ESP teachers, strongly believe in the need for retraining the teachers for the effective implementation of the OBE-based pedagogies and assessments. According to them, teachers must be trained with Spady's 5 P's because they can provide complete understanding regarding the OBE system. The study exemplifies that OBE can be beneficial if profound awareness is developed about the OBE principles, as was also stated by Macayan (2017). For this, early in-depth planning is required by the institutes to develop course outlines and contents and training teachers for the change. After planning, it is necessary to ensure proper implementation and consistency for assessments because they also play a significant role in achieving the desired results of the OBE framework.

Participants of the study have fundamental knowledge that is insufficient to achieve engineering program outcomes, and there has to have 5P's in-depth awareness so that students' learning outcomes can be improved. For example, although course designing, lecture delivery and assessments with PLOs and CLOs have been initiated, there is a constant need to train teachers about these components so that they can make the overall learning process efficient for students. Similarly, the underlying assumption of OBE being practical, focusing on providing learners autonomy for a systematic learning process, must be understood. Without

addressing the gap between the learners' existing proficiencies and the teachers' expectations, OBE, with a partial shift, would miss the mark for effective implementation.

Although OBE is effectively to be implemented in higher education (Naqvi et al., 2019), participants shared that designing a course relevant to the requirements of the OBE model for the ESP classroom is tough with limited resources. The present study also supports the already presented belief that OBE in Pakistan is currently in its transitional phase (Shaheen, 2019) due to the challenges mentioned in the findings above. Furthermore, there is a need to develop more awareness and understanding towards OBE in the education department, as mentioned by Pirzada and Gull (2019). Similarly, a study by Manzoor et al. (2017) has also stated that OBE's transformation process, which helps improve student outcomes and educational processes, must be sorted out to provide benefits to the becoming engineers. It will bridge the gap to improve engineering education in Pakistan which is indeed the need of the time.

The current study further supports the findings of Passow and Passow (2017) that engineering studies should work "effectively, design solutions, apply knowledge, apply skills, and solve problems", as problem-solving is considered the core of engineering practice. Moreover, the findings of Benson et al. (2010) and Kirn and Benson (2018) that engineering students must know how to solve problems after thinking critically demonstrate that engineers' education must be addressed with appropriate learning materials in ESP courses. In education, engineering students are expected to face a "complex and unpredictable set of social interactions" (Secules et al., 2021). It is because their careers are interconnected with their studies, learning resources and methods of teaching. Therefore, English teachers must maintain these students' skills with the best available resources and teaching practices. It is also essential to adopt the original Washington Accord graduate attributes while reviewing learning resources.

Conclusion and Limitations

The present study concludes that teachers' understanding of OBE is limited, and they face certain constraints in implementing it in English language classrooms at a Pakistani university for engineering students. It also confirms Shaheen (2019) finding that teachers lack the training to implement OBE in classrooms fully. Therefore, they must be provided with adequate training to execute it successfully. However, the implementation of OBE is not dependent on teachers only; active involvement of policymakers, institutions and students is also required. Moreover, further studies are required to experiment with students' perceptions, teachers' handling of such challenges and further experimentation in OBE teaching set-up.

Furthermore, in engineering education, English teachers must ensure that their courses are taught appropriately and sufficiently with Spady's Ps of OBE. For this, preconceived notions about education must be shifted towards a flexible approach, as highlighted by Kamran et al. (2020) (Qadir et al., 2020). The shift from traditional teaching styles to a learner-centred approach requires extensive planning of the engineering department of the universities in Pakistan. To manage this process effectively, English teachers need support from the administration and adequate training that will enable them to build future engineers in a country by following the OBE method, as was clearly highlighted by Shaheen (2019). It has been observed that a challenge in the success of OBE lies in the "paradigm shift"; it is the institutions' administration's duty to shift the mode of teaching from conventional to OBE by providing training to teachers and monitoring its implementation.

The present study is limited to establishing work on Outcome-Based Education (OBE) to share one Pakistani university teacher's experiences and provide evidence of OBE practices for policymakers. It is limited to ESP teachers' constraints while implementing OBE for engineering students in a Pakistani university. ESP teachers, who were part of both traditional and OBE, were interviewed to have a deeper understanding of their challenges.

Implications and Suggestions

The study has implications for teachers' training and material development specific to OBE in ESP Pakistani classrooms. Developing ESP course materials for engineering students requires sufficient time, but teachers are primarily engaged in teaching preparation and other administrative duties, as mentioned (Aniroh, 2019). Although it is a time-consuming process that requires preparation, materials developers or course moderators must show consistency in developing the course and choosing the OBE method in implementing the course outlines of engineering programs. In the early phases, it is time-consuming, but training and collective efforts can minimize the burden on teachers and become fruitful for future engineers of Pakistan.

The teachers should be equipped with the skills to handle the pedagogies as required by the OBE format technically. Also, they need to maintain that the learners' motivation is crucial for achieving the learning objectives of ESP courses. The material development is more or less fixed in the traditional ESP domain, where the focus is more on using contextualized material. However, OBE requires well-thought-out planning to use

material that effectively fits into the smaller assessment units. It can be done by developing material based on teaching reflections and encouraging teachers to explore new experiences as researchers.

Moreover, administration and parents must come forward to support OBE-based education equally for males and females despite any cultural norms, as it may affect the betterment of Pakistani society and progress in the engineering domain. The present study further suggests a need to explore students' perspectives, results and other subject teachers' views about OBE. It will provide an understanding of OBE implementation and will help improve engineering education in Pakistan.

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